

REPORTS BETWEEN THE NORTH ATLANTIC TREATY ORGANIZATION - NATO AND THE EUROPEAN UNION

Dr. NUHI OSMANI

¹Flensburg University Germany (Ma. sc International Criminal Law University of Pristina Kosovo – Lawyer Law Faculty of Pristina University Kosovo), Pristina Kosovo. Email nuhi.osmani@rks-gov.net

Dr. PETRIT NIMANI

Professor at the Faculty of Law at the University "Haxhi Zeka" in Peja, Republic of Kosovo.
Correspondent author Email: petrit.nimani@unhz.eu

ALBAN MALIQI

Lecture at the Faculty of Law at the University "Haxhi Zeka" in Peja Republic of Kosovo and “College Universium” Pristina Republic of Kosovo. Email: alban.maliqui@unhz.eu

Abstract

After World War II ended, and from which Europe was the main arena of fighting it caused many material consequences and the death of many people and all of this, the heads of states discussed the creation of an alliance that would ensure collective defense, which was created in 1949 as the North Atlantic Treaty Organization – NATO. Part of which were also the most influential countries of Europe at the time, then the European Union - EU was created in 1951, where it was founded with the aim of the cooperation of the European countries coming out of the war in economic terms. But over the years it was considered reasonable that the EU also have the Foreign and Security Policy that was officially formed by the Maastricht Treaty and that will be examined in the following paper, where member states are required to cooperate with intercommunal organizations, maintain a common position in international forums and support common foreign and security policy. The main purpose of NATO (North Atlantic Treaty Organization) is to preserve the freedom and security of its member countries through political and military means. NATO is committed to the peaceful resolution of disputes. If diplomatic efforts fail, it has the military capacity to undertake crisis management operations. They are carried out based on Article 5 of the Washington Treaty, the founding treaty of NATO, or based on a UN (United Nations Organization) mandate, alone or in cooperation with other countries and international organizations. The European Union is a unique political and economic partnership between 27 democratic European countries aiming at peace, prosperity and freedom for its 500 million citizens, in a fairer and safer world. It is a constantly evolving structure which has no historical precedent. The primary legislation of the EU are the treaties signed between member states. These treaties lay down the basic policies of the EU, establish its institutional structure, legislative procedure and powers. Some of the main treaties are: the EEC Treaty of Rome (1957), the Single European Act (1986), the Treaty of Maastricht (1992), the Amsterdam Treaty (1997) and the Lisbon Treaty (2007). The EU's main institutions are: The European Parliament, the European Council, the Council of the European Union, and the European Commission. NATO and the EU are essential partners that share common values, strategic interests in the majority of member state. In recent years, the two organizations have developed closer cooperation, focused on concrete results and improved security for European citizens. This ranges from cyber defense and addressing hybrid threats, through maritime security to building the capacity of partners beyond our borders. NATO and the EU are working to enlarge their cooperation in addressing current and emerging security challenges. The EU and NATO were founded and operate on the same values and strategic interests, particularly in terms of issues related to security, defense and crisis management.

Keywords: EU-NATO relations, strategic partnership, Global Strategy for EU Foreign and Security Policy, European Security, Transatlantic relationship.

Preliminary reports on security policy in the EU

The first EU security policy of the organization is the "Western European Union" (henceforth WEU) which was a product of the Brussels Treaty of 1948, an agreement signed between Belgium, France, Luxembourg, the Netherlands and the United Kingdom to ensure collective defense and to facilitate cooperation in economic, social and cultural issues.⁴ In 1954 the Treaty of Brussels was strengthened and modified to include West Germany and Italy, to end the occupation of West Germany and to include West Germany in NATO, and the WEU was established on 6 May 1955.⁵ But the efforts of the WEU did not develop much and it remained in the shadow of NATO, since most of its power was transferred to the international organization of NATO.⁶ In addition to the Western European Union, other efforts to create a common defense and security policy were the plans of Fouché, Elise, Davignon, Genshin-Klombos ect. Where Fouché's plan was designed to create an alternative to the US and the Soviet Union, the plan focused on greater European cooperation to create a common foreign and security policy.⁷ The Elysée Treaty was a bilateral treaty signed between France and Germany that strengthen ties between the two countries in terms of security and diplomacy.⁸

While the Gensher-Colombo report of 1981 was intended to weaken the power of the veto and make a stronger political cooperation for the EU, but also the main goals on this path were the definition of a common European foreign policy and the extension of powers of the Community in new areas, including defense and justice.⁹

Relations between NATO and the EU

NATO, as a military organization with several powerful states that are members of the EU at the same time, attaches great importance to this relationship. The EU attaches more importance to diplomatic means for conflict resolution than to the development of a common security and defense policy and the preservation of its territorial integrity. So, it seems as if the military component of NATO, which acts as a military alliance, and the civilian component of the EU, which uses diplomacy and its civilian missions before excellence to solve and manage crisis situations, complement each other.¹⁰

Today, the EU and NATO face numerous challenges and share common strategic interests, cooperate to mitigate the crises that are threatening them and strive together to provide support to their partners in different regions of the world, including facing hybrid threats, increasing sustainability, building defense capacities, cyber defense, maritime security, etc. The EU is a very special partner for NATO as they have the majority of members in common and have the same values and also face the same challenges and threats.¹¹

Over the years, many meetings and summits were held within the framework of the continuity of EU-NATO relations. Such as the 2010 Lisbon Summit where the Allies underlined their determination to improve the NATO-EU strategic partnership.¹²

According to point 11 of the Summit, "NATO and the European Union (EU) share common values and strategic interests and are working side by side in crisis management operations.

Therefore, we are determined to improve the NATO-EU strategic partnership, as agreed by our two organizations."¹³

The next meeting was scheduled in 2016 at the Warsaw Summit where point 10 of the summit decisions was about cooperation with the European Union where NATO took its relationship with the European Union to another level, and also expanded its cooperation with the EU- in the Mediterranean, where information sharing and coordination can make us more effective in dealing with illegal migration, terrorism and other challenges.¹⁴

The next summit of the continuity of EU-NATO relations was the Brussels Summit in 2018, where in points 69 and 70 it is reiterated once again that the European Union remains a unique and essential partner for NATO, and will continue to strengthen this relationship even more further in the spirit of full mutual openness, transparency, complementarity and respect for the different mandates of the organizations, decision-making autonomy and institutional integrity.¹⁵

This cooperation will always serve to increase the security of citizens, the promotion of peace and stability in the Euro-Atlantic area and beyond. Even at NATO's 2021 Brussels summit, NATO recognizes the importance of a stronger and more capable European defense. Among other things, point 65 of the Summit states that the political dialogue between NATO and the EU remains essential for the advancement of this cooperation.¹⁶

Through this summit, NATO and the EU deepen their cooperation, making progress in a number of areas within 74 joint proposals, including the context of the COVID-19 pandemic.¹⁷ NATO and the EU are also increasingly involved in each other's exercises. Working together in this area, NATO and the EU have long cooperated on crisis management and operations.¹⁸

Both Operation EUFOR in Bosnia and Herzegovina and in Kosovo, NATO's KFOR peacekeeping forces work with the EU's Rule of Law mission (EULEX) to bring peace and stability to the region. As for testing the hypothesis of the work, we come to the conclusion that the EU is still militarily dependent on NATO for one of the reasons that the largest financier of NATO operations is the USA, that is the economic impossibility of the European Union states and the allies' policy to meet defense spending, and not only since the EU is dependent on NATO in many aspects of planning, command, control and logistics.¹⁹ But it is not far-fetched that these two organizations also have disagreements with each other, since there are member states that are not part of both at the same time, the concrete case is the situation of Cyprus and Turkey, since Cyprus is a member of the EU and Turkey is member with a great influence in NATO. Turkey's territorial claims against Cyprus, which was recently admitted to the European Union, have brought many problems between these two organizations. NATO requires every country that shares security information to be a member of the Partnership for Peace (PfP) program. Admission to the PfP program requires unanimous approval by all NATO countries. However, Turkey has not recognized the Republic of Cyprus since 1963 and blocked its accession to the PfP. Cyprus joined the European Union in 2004.²⁰ The European Union and NATO have not been able to cooperate fully since Cyprus became a member of the European Union in 2004. As Cyprus is not allowed to participate in the meetings

of the Partnership for Peace Program. This has aggravated the relations between the European Union and NATO since the European Union insists that Cyprus should also participate in those meetings, while NATO does not allow such a thing. But the situation is the same even now where Finland and Sweden have applied for membership in NATO and are members of the EU, and the problem is that Turkey is opposing, which is expected to be seen in the future.

Joint Declaration on European Defense

Before Saint-Malo, in 1993 the Common Foreign and Security Policy (CFSP) was established by the Maastricht Treaty as the second of the three pillars that formed the European Union.²¹ According to the treaty, member states are required above all to support the common foreign and security policy.²² Since the European Union at that time was essentially a "civilian power".²³ All EU member states, both individually and collectively, have always participated in military planning and procurement in cooperation with the NATO organization and the WEU.²⁴ After the Cold War, the greatest strategic destabilization arose from the wars that took place in the breakup of Yugoslavia, which also increased the risk to the security of the European Union. The United States did not want to get involved and the EU had no powers, so the situation became even more delicate than it appeared.²⁵ In December 1998, the Franco-British Declaration of Saint Malo marked the first major step towards the European Defense and Security Policy (ESDP).²⁶ The Declaration of Saint Malo represents a historical moment in the history of the construction of a European defense and security policy: Where the European Union (EU) became competent in security matters and discussed military matters (staff, intelligence, weaponry).²⁷ In this Joint Declaration on European Defense approved during the meeting in Saint Malo. Representatives of participating states such as France and the United Kingdom agreed that "the European Union needs to be in a position to play its full role on the international stage"²⁸ And it must have the capacity for autonomous action, supported by credible military forces, the means to decide on their use and the readiness to act, in order to respond to international crises".²⁹ But above all within the framework of the summit it was emphasized that Europe needed to strengthen the armed forces in order to respond to the risks that could threaten them.³⁰

European Security and Defense policy

Relations between NATO and the European Union began in 2001 building on steps taken during the 1990s to promote greater European responsibility in defense matters.³¹ The Treaty of Amsterdam, which entered into force on May 1, 1999, came as a response to the need to create a new institutional structure that could successfully cope with the accession of new states.³² This Treaty marked the beginning of the establishment of the ESDP.³³ For the first time in modern history, a number of independent states have chosen of their own free will to form a traditional alliance to coordinate activities in the field of security and defense.³⁴ Then the political principles that are based on the relationship between the EU and NATO are defined in the formal NATO-EU declaration of December 2002 on the PESMI. The 2002 NATO-EU Declaration on a European Security and Defense Policy (ESDP) set out the political principles underpinning the relationship between the two organizations and reaffirmed that the EU provided access to NATO's planning capabilities for EU military operations. In the period when

the war in Kosovo was becoming more and more critical. NATO openly gave its blessing to PMSE, which was also referred to as IMSE, and that the new European project should be developed in close cooperation with NATO.³⁵ And within this situation, the Berlin Plus agreement was created, which was a series of agreements signed between NATO and the EU that came from the conclusion of the NATO Summit in Washington.³⁶ Where this agreement discussed and addressed some very important points such as the NATO-EU Security Agreement; Secure access to NATO planning capabilities for EU-led crisis management operations (CMO); Availability of NATO tools and capacities for the EU; Procedures for the Release, Monitoring, Return and Recovery of NATO Assets and Capabilities, etc.³⁷

These are just some of the main points through which the cooperation between the European Union and NATO works. NATO and the European Union signed these measures after the September 11 attacks that took place in the United States of America. These measures came as a result of preventing crises, armed conflicts... The attack on the twin towers in America scared NATO and Europe. Could be the target of these terrorist attacks. With the entry into force of the Treaty of Nice in 2003, it brought changes related to the PEMS, where it marked the establishment of three permanent military and political institutions: the Policy and Security Committee, the Military Committee, and the Military Headquarters.³⁸ Despite the changes that the Treaty of Nice brought to the second pillar, defense continued to remain a national issue where the main role in the field of armaments was played by the Member States, as they were the largest purchasers and investors of military equipment.³⁹

Conclusions

Over the years, the European Union has expressed its continuous will to create a foreign security policy. Despite its efforts for a security policy for the European Union, it still remains under the shadow of NATO for the reasons mentioned above. After the creation of the Foreign and Security Policy as a separate pillar envisaged by the Maastricht Treaty, the European Union began to identify itself as a separate entity and separate from NATO, despite having common member states, and that the entry into force of the Treaty of Lisbon marked a new phase in the security and defense policy of the EU, now called PEMS, which was not accompanied by the creation of the appropriate institutional structure. Despite the merger of the "three pillars" structure, PEMS remains a separate field that has its own rules and procedures. The conflicts in the former Yugoslavia found the EU unprepared in terms of capacity to cope with a conflict of such proportions, not only in terms of geographical scope but also the complexity of the issues. The EU failed to speak with a single voice and the way it knew best to address the conflicts was the diplomatic one, leaving the biggest burden of decision-making to the UN and NATO.

The EU and NATO today have very good relations between them. Their future is seen from joint engagements as history has shown that they have excellent cooperation such as the EU Engagement in Afghanistan, EUPOL, NATO and EU Engagement in the Somali Peninsula, as well as NATO and the EU, through their mechanisms and local policies, have often tried, in

some cases more effectively than others, to raise citizens' awareness. But above all, the EU and NATO have shown a fantastic relationship in the fight against terrorism.

Biography

Books

1. Nello, Senior Susan. "The European Union – Economics, Policies and History", MC Graw – Hill Education, January 2012.
2. Howorth, Jolyon. "Politika e Sigurisë dhe e Mbrojtjes në Bashkimin Evropian". Palgrave Macmillan Universum Press, 2013
3. Klaus-Diter Borçard- ABC-ja e të Drejtës së Bashkimit Evropian., Zyra e Botimeve të Bashkimit Evropian, 2013 <http://integrimi-ne-be.puneteshastme.gov.al/wp-content/uploads/2020/04/3-ABC-e-s%C3%AB-Drejt%C3%ABs-s%C3%AB-Bashkimit-Evropian.pdf>
4. Laurie Bounanno dhe Neill Nugent-Politikat dhe Proceset e Politikave të Bashkimit Evropian-Universum Press, 2013

Other sources

1. "The signing of the Élysée Treaty (22 January 1963)" <https://www.cvce.eu/en/education/unit-content/-/unit/c3c5e6c5-1241-471d-9e3a-dc6e7202ca16/3947ea20-4ae8-4717-8e6d-7bb3dd88821f> Qasur më 23.05.2022.
2. Cuccia, Deborah. "The Genscher-Colombo Plan: A forgotten page in the European Integration History". Nomos e-library. https://www.nomos-elibrary.de/10.5771/0947-9511-2018-1-59.pdf?download_full_pdf=1
3. European Union "EU-NATO cooperation – Factsheets". https://www.eeas.europa.eu/eeas/eu-nato-cooperation-factsheets_en Qasur më 25.05.2022.
4. Gegout, Catherine . "The french and british change in position in the CESDP: a security community and historical -institutionalist perspective". 2002. <https://www.cairn.info/revue-politique-europeenne-2002-4-page-62.htm> Qasur më 24.05.2022
5. Howorth, Jolyon. "Saint-Malo plus five: An interim Assessment of ESDP". Notre Europe. 3003. <https://institutdelors.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/08/policypaper7-1.pdf> Qasur më 31.05.2022.
6. Janigian, Alan M. "The Cypriot-Turkish conflict and NATO-European Union cooperation", Monterey, California: Naval Postgraduate School. 2017. https://calhoun.nps.edu/bitstream/handle/10945/55628/17Jun_Janigian_Alان.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y Qasur më 24.04.2022
7. Lorca, María. "The reform Treaty: Its impact on the Common Foreign and Security Policy". 2007. <http://aei.pitt.edu/8209/1/LorcaCFSP-EUMA07.pdf> Qasur më 25.05.2022
8. NATO. "Brussels Summit Communiqué". 2021. https://www.nato.int/cps/en/natohq/news_185000.htm Qasur më 31.02.2022
9. NATO. "Brussels Summit Declaration". 2018. https://www.nato.int/cps/en/natohq/official_texts_156624.htm Qasur më 31.05.2022
10. NATO. "Lisbon Summit Declaration" Issued by the Heads of State and Government participating in the meeting of the North Atlantic Council in Lisbon. 2010. https://www.nato.int/cps/em/natohq/official_texts_68828.htm Qasur më 25.05.2022

11. NATO. “NATO – EU Relations” Factsheets. November 2021. E qasshme në https://www.nato.int/nato_static_fl2014/assets/pdf/2021/11/pdf/2111-factsheet-nato-eu-en.pdf Qasur më 24.04.2022.
12. NATO. “NATO – EU Relations”... 2021. https://www.nato.int/nato_static_fl2014/assets/pdf/2021/11/pdf/2111-factsheet-nato-eu-en.pdf Qasur më 31.05.2022.
13. NATO. “Summit Guide. Lisbon Summit - 19-20 November 2010”. 2010. https://www.nato.int/cps/en/natohq/topics_67814.htm Qasur më 25.05.2022
14. NATO. “Warsaw Summit Key Decisions”. 2016. https://www.nato.int/nato_static_fl2014/assets/pdf/pdf_2017_02/20170206_1702-factsheet-warsaw-summit-key-en.pdf Qasur më 31.05.2022
15. NATO: “Relations with the European Union”, https://www.nato.int/cps/en/natohq/topics_49217.htm Qasur më 24.04.2022,
16. Shkreli, Yrfet “Politika e Jashtme dhe e Sigurisë e Bashkimit Europian. Marrëdhëniet NATO – BE”. Universiteti i Tiranës. 2018. <https://unitir.edu.al/wp-content/uploads/2018/07/Doktoratura-Yrfet-Shkreli.pdf#toolbar=0> Qasur më 31.02.2022.
17. Waugh, Tim. “Berlin Plus agreement”. https://www.europarl.europa.eu/meetdocs/2004_2009/documents/dv/berlinplus_/berlinplus_en.pdf Qasur më 24.04.2022.